

Influence of NCDC’s Radio Campaigns on COVID-19 Protocol Compliance among Residents of Akure, Ondo State

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Abstract

This study looked into the influence of NCDC’s radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol compliance among residents of Akure Ondo State. The objectives of the study set out to: examine the level of exposure to NCDC’s radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol compliance and investigate the extent of compliance to COVID-19 Safety protocols arising from exposure to NCDC’s radio Campaign. The study adopted survey research design, through the use of a structured questionnaire to generate responses from a population of 360,268 residents of Akure, A multistage sampling technique was adopted to select the sample size of Three Hundred and Ninety-Nine (399). Findings revealed that there is a considerable level of exposure to radio campaigns on COVID 19 safety protocols among residents of Akure in Ondo State. It was also revealed that there is a significant relationship between exposure to NCDC’s radio campaigns on COVID-19 and COVID-19 protocol compliance among Akure residents. The study affirmed that the radio serves as a viable medium of health communication which influences compliance with COVID-19 safety protocol among Akure residents. It was also observed that NCDC’s radio campaigns were adequate to prompt Akure residents to practice the safety protocols messages of the radio campaign which also rightly educated Akure residents generally about the virus as well as influenced a great level of compliance among the residents. Radio stations in Akure and NCDC should continue campaigns on compliance with COVID-19 protocol in Akure even though, the virus infection rate has reduced as this will constantly bring to the consciousness of the need to practice compliance to preventive measures and further enhance the gains recorded against COVID-19.

Keywords: NCDC, Radio Campaigns, COVID-19, Compliance, Akure

Background to the study

The mass media are known vehicles for transmitting information to a large heterogeneous audience. The primary purpose of the existence of the mass media is to distil information which is eventually disseminated to the public. Hence the media, through this information, guide the decision-making process of its audience while educating and entertaining them simultaneously (Daramola, 2012). As an essential agent of socialisation, the media provide knowledge and information on various issues at the local, national and international levels. Media do not only provide information and updates on various issues and happenings but also give a direction to the public for making up their judgments and perceptions, as well as make the public embrace a new favourable and healthy way of life (Akpobo, 2015; Ebenezer, 2021).

One of the important roles in recent times that the media have been playing is that of health communication through various campaigns to effect a change in the behaviours of people in the society. Ebenezer (2021, p. 7) avers that “an issue of great importance for public health today is how to mount programmes that change behaviour to improve the health of our population”. This behoves the media to intensify efforts of intervention in public health to make the society safe and prevent people from contracting any ravaging disease which poses threat to human lives through adequate information. Be that as it may, there is an observed effort by the media to meet with its social responsibility in this regard in contemporary times. Akpobo (2015) maintains that, in Nigeria's struggle for sustainable health development, the mass media remain a critical component and valuable instrument because the mass media have proved to be concerned about the people’s health through their regular health communication on health issues as well as campaigns on drug

abuse, vaccinations/immunisations, maternal health care, family planning programmes, healthy living practices, prevention practices, disease cure eradication.

It is generally believed that the media in Nigeria have been actively involved in promoting the health of the nation through proper information dissemination to avail the audience the opportunity of making informed decisions on a particular health issue that is prevalent in the society. The media employ some forms of health communication interventions to influence behaviour and attitude of their audiences on any given health related messages. In addition, mass media helps agencies to expand their reach with vital information in the face of health challenges including outbreak of pandemic thereby preventing further risks to the people's well-being. The media thus serve as a major link between the people and vital health information. This accounts for the position of Ufuophu-Biri and Bebenimibo (2021) that, during a disease outbreak, a critical job of the media is to influence the public's attitude, perception, and behaviour so that they take the proper precautions to avoid contracting and spreading the disease. This has often been referred to as health communication, and it is premised on the social responsibility of the media to properly enlighten the public and disseminate well-researched information on possible ways to promote their health and, by extension, the health of the society.

The radio happens to be one media outlet that can carry out effective and efficient health communication to a considerable extent. This comes from the fact that, unlike other media, radio is a relatively accessible medium through which information is disseminated to a large audience. It is a medium that connects people from far and near places, bringing them information about the happenings in their environment through the use of the electromagnetic spectrum and it transcends the boundary of space and time as well as crossing the barrier of literacy (Daramola, 2012). The realisation of the role played by the media in terms of passing across useful information and also curbing false information, that could cause panic and affect the behaviour of people towards response to health crises notably, the recent COVID-19 outbreak, informed the undertaking of this study which seeks to examine the impact of Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) radio campaigns tagged: "Our fight against COVID-19 is a collective effort take responsibility, All hands and wear your face mask to reduce the risk of COVID-19 spread", on protocol compliance among residents of Akure, Ondo State.

Statement of the problem

The outbreak of COVID-19 unarguably took the world unaware, therefore, leaving affected countries to suffer devastating deaths among citizens as well as economic breakdown, among others, beginning from December 2019 to date (Olapegba et al., 2020). The media have been noted to play an essential role during the outbreak of health crises across the globe, and this was observed to play out in the outbreak of the Coronavirus disease. Through tracking and live updates, the media allowed for timely interventions by the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) and the World Health Organisation (WHO), enabling a rapid and widespread reach of public health communications. This, therefore, led to an upward trend for the promotion of health and hygiene practices by encouraging people to adopt safe health practices such as hand washing, use of face coverings, and social distancing. Also, the media projected daily illness-preventing guideline (Olapegba et al., 2020).

Although there is a truism in the above positions, it is observed in the study of Iheanacho et al. (2021) that less study has been carried out in Nigeria on the influential role played through radio campaigns to bring about compliance with COVID-19 protocol. Furthermore, Nigerians are not conforming to COVID-19 guidelines, and they perceive media campaigns on COVID-19 in a negative way, with beliefs that it projects fear and panic about the COVID-19 virus (Odubanjo, 2020). Besides, there are more television campaigns on COVID-19 protocol compliance than radio campaigns in Nigeria (Apuke & Omar 2021). Notwithstanding, there has been a high rate of daily confirmed cases and death cases recorded in Nigeria, which as of 2022 stands at 254,637 recorded cases and 3,142 deaths, according to NCDC. In the case of Ondo State, which is ranked 10th with confirmed cases of the

virus in Nigeria. There are 5,173 confirmed cases with 109 deaths (NCDC, 2022). This, therefore, leaves the question of NCDC's radio campaigns' potency, on compliance with COVID-19 protocols. Hence, this study was geared towards examining the influence of NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol compliance among residents of Akure in Ondo State.

Objectives of the study

The general objective of this study was to examine the influence of NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol compliance among residents of Akure, Ondo State.

The specific objectives are to:

- i. examine the level of exposure to NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol among residents of Akure in Ondo State; and
- ii. investigate the extent of compliance to NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol among residents of Akure in Ondo State.

Hypothesis

The under listed null hypothesis was formulated from the research questions raised in this study and was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₁: There is no significant relationship between exposure to NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 and COVID-19 protocol compliance among residents of Akure in Ondo State.

Literature review

The concept of radio campaign and NCDC's radio campaigns

Radio campaigns are an efficient tool to influence the public opinion because radio reaches a wider audience than any other medium, and is accessible to people who are otherwise isolated by geography, conflict, illiteracy or poverty (Wateraid & WSSCC, 2013). Due to the risk associated with the COVID-19, broadcast media constantly churned out several COVID-19 campaigns to inform the people on how to stay safe from the virus. Of course, the mass media cannot cure virus but can curb its spread.

In Nigeria, the Federal Ministry of Health, in collaboration with agencies such as NCDC, NOA and the National Primary Health Care Development Agency, have undertaken a programme to disseminate messages on COVID-19 prevention and symptoms through health facility workers. NCDC public health information campaigns have been transmitted via radio and television, which have explicitly attempted to counter COVID-19 misinformation. During the pandemic era, it successfully sensitised the general public about the dangers of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) sensitised the people of Akure, Ondo state with series of radio campaigns reiterating the need to curb the spread of COVID-19 by following certain protocols. According to NCDC, the summary of all COVID-19 guidelines and safety precautions is for Nigerians of all tribes and tongues, as well as non-Nigerians in the country, to take responsibility by participating in the critical race to halt and end the pandemic for the good of all. The radio campaigns are multi-language mass media campaigns, which are being promoted across Nigeria in Hausa, Igbo, Yoruba, Pidgin, and English via print, radio, and social media, are based on the essential NCDC instructions and safety procedures for preventing the spread of the novel Coronavirus. The radio campaigns highlight the need for citizens to take responsibility for their safety through safe practises like hand washing, social distancing and not touching their faces. Adherence to these instructions will curb the spread of the virus and also keep the people of Akure in Ondo State safe.

The content of "All Hands" radio campaign states that:

Have your hands washed or sanitised frequently, always cough or sneeze into your elbow and no going out without a face mask, the distance of at least two amps length should be maintained, stay indoors and self-isolate if you feel sick.

The NCDC radio campaigns urge citizen to maintain precautionary measures against COVID-19 during celebrations, the recommendation to stay in one's state and to self-isolate for 14 days after returning from an international trip is crucial. If one experiences symptoms such as frequent coughing, sneezing, fever, or shortness of breath, one should call their state's emergency number or the NCDC's toll-free number for immediate assistance.

COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria

According to Chibuike and Bashar (2020) Nigeria recorded its first COVID-19 case, of an Italian national on February 27, 2020. According to NCDC the virus originated from Wuhan in China at the end of 2019 and has infected over six million people and led to the death of over 300,000 worldwide. The Nigeria's index case was confirmed by the Virology Laboratory of the Lagos University Teaching Hospital when a suspected Italian Man who arrived Nigeria from Milan on February 24, 2020 on the Turkish Airline. Even though the index case came to Nigeria through the Murtala Muhammad International Airport Lagos, the fact that he was first suspected to have had the virus in Ogun state meant that all the people who had contact with him are 39 people, including four health workers at his company's clinic had to be quarantined by the Ogun State Government, and contact tracing of the people on the same flight with him was initiated by the Lagos State Government and the Nigeria NCDC (Ohiwerei & Okosun, 2021). The COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria from inception of the first case in the country saw to a rise in the number of affected persons which as at September 2020 rose to about 56,017 positive cases, with more cases recorded in the last quarter of 2020 alongside deaths of many Nigerians (NCDC, 2020).

Theoretical review

The social responsibility theory of the press gives to it the duty and role of responsibility and responsiveness to certain principles which are centred mainly on public interest. The report of Hutchin commission set by the United States government in 1947. The nucleus of the social responsibility theory is the traditional role of the media as the watchdog of the society, disseminating fair, objective and balanced information without hindrance. The social responsibility theory according to Jubril (1997) cited in Duyile (2015, p. 172) "assigns to the press, in other words, the watchdog role which in essence means that the press should be people-centred". From the foregoing, one key function of the press is social responsibility to their audience.

The social responsibility theory is applicable to this study as in fulfilling its duty to the society, the media through these principles of this theory is expected to objectively and accurately report issues that are of importance without bias to the general public. It is the responsibility of the media to provide timely and correct information for health education and the promotion of prevention strategies. Therefore, based on the principle of social responsibility theory, it is expected that the media become the primary source of information to the public in event of disasters and emergencies. Enlightening the society about COVID-19 risk and also educate them on the prevention protocol compliance.

Methodology

The study adopted survey research design; the sample size for the study was 399 residents of Akure, Ondo State, using Taro Yamane formula (1967) to determine the sample size. A multistage sampling technique was adopted to select the sample size proportionally drawn from Akure South and Akure North local government areas. Out of the 399 copies of the questionnaire administered, 346 copies were returned and valid for analysis. A hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance using Pearson Product Movement Correlation (PPMC).

Data analysis and presentation

Research question one: What is the level of exposure to NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol compliance among Akure residents, Ondo State?

Table 1: Level of exposure to NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol compliance among Akure residents, Ondo State

Level of exposure	VLE (5)		LE (4)		M (3)		L (2)		VL (1)		N (0)		Mean	SD
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
I am exposed to radio frequency of the major radio stations in Akure such as Adaba FM, Orange FM, Breeze FM and OSRC.	132	38.2	99	28.6	68	19.7	30	8.7	17	4.9	0	0	3.86	1.16
I listen to radio campaigns about COVID-19 in Akure on the major radio stations.	76	22.0	93	26.9	126	34.6	32	9.2	37	10.7	0	0	3.33	1.33
I have come across radio campaigns about COVID-19 compliance protocol on Adaba FM, Orange FM, Breeze FM and OSRC to a great extent.	143	41.3	124	35.8	12	3.5	27	7.8	23	6.6	17	4.9	3.82	1.46
I listen to radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol compliance on major radio stations at least two to five times a week.	72	20.7	102	29.4	132	38.0	27	7.8	5	1.4	8	2.3	3.86	1.16
I am exposed to radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol compliance on major radio station more than five times a week.	84	24.2	76	21.9	125	36.0	31	8.9	18	5.2	11	3.2	3.76	1.08

Weighted mean = 3.09; Arithmetic Mean = 18.6372s; Standard Deviation = 1.238122

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

Keys: VLE= Very Large Extent (5), LE= Large Extent (4), M= Moderate (3), L= Low Extent (2), VL= Very Low (1), N= None (0), SD= Standard Deviation. Decision rule: 1.00-1.99 Low Influence, 2.00-2.99 Moderate Influence, 3.00-3.99 High Influence, 4.00-4.99 Very High Influence, 5.00 and above Extremely High Influence. Criterion mean 3.0.

Table 1 presents the results on the level of exposure to NCDC’s radio campaigns on compliance with COVID-19 protocol among Akure residents, Ondo State. It was revealed that residents of Akure, listen to NCDC’s radio campaigns on COVID-19 in Akure on the major radio stations to a moderate extent (Mean=3.8266). This implies that radio in Akure, serves as a viable medium through which residents got informed about COVID-19 outbreak. In like manner, Akure residents have come across radio campaigns about COVID-19 compliance protocol on Adaba FM, Orange FM, Breeze FM and OSRC to a great extent to a very large extent (Mean=3.8266). This is a pointer to the fact that the major radio stations in Akure lived up to expectations in fulfilling their social responsibility of correlating the society and reporting uncomplimentary occurrences such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

Research question two: What is the extent of compliance to NCDC’s radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol among Akure residents of Ondo State?

Table 2: Extent of compliance to NCDC’s radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol among Akure residents of Ondo State

Extent of compliance	VLE (5)		LE (4)		M (3)		L (2)		VL (1)		N (0)		Mean	SD
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
I believe people comply with COVID-19 protocol in Akure based on their exposure to NCDC’s radio campaigns.	84	24.2	76	21.9	125	36.0	26	7.5	21	6.1	14	4.0	3.75	1.10

I personally comply with the directives from NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol.	104	30.0	37	10.7	94	27.1	92	26.5	15	4.3	4	1.2	3.68	1.21
NCDC's radio campaigns on compliance with COVID-19 protocol communicated the intended messages to residents of Akure.	68	19.6	144	41.5	88	25.4	11	3.2	22	6.3	13	3.7	3.88	0.97
Generally, I believe there is a high level of compliance with NCDC's COVID-19 protocols among people in Akure.	68	19.6	131	37.8	84	24.2	28	8.1	28	8.1	7	2.0	3.86	0.93
Based on my exposure to NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocols in Akure, my level of compliance has increased considerably.	84	24.2	122	35.2	80	23.1	44	12.7	13	3.7	3	0.9	3.81	1.02

Weighted mean = 3.82; Arithmetic Mean = 19.1; Standard Deviation = 5.23449

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 2 presents the results on the extent of compliance to NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol among Akure residents of Ondo State. The result revealed that most of the residents of Akure said that their compliance to NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol among Akure residents of Ondo State is moderate (Mean=3.7524). The implication of this is that although there is a high level of awareness through radio broadcast campaigns on COVID-19 in Akure, the level of compliance among Akure residents of Ondo State is not as expected as compliance is at a moderate level and this could be attributed to possible lack of believe in the existence of the virus in the first place.

As regards individual compliance with the directives from NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol in Akure, majority of the residents personally comply with the directives from NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol to a very large extent (Mean=3.6896). This implies that there is more individual believability of the existence of the virus based on information from NCDC's radio campaigns. Hence, the recorded level of compliance among individuals in Akure. This implies that the media, through radio campaigns have done proper research into the COVID-19 pandemic to have passed across accurate and verified information on the virus.

Additionally, results from the analysis presented in Table 2 indicated that Akure residents believe there is a high level of compliance with NCDC's COVID-19 protocols among people in Akure to a large extent (Mean=3.8684). The implication of this is that residents of Akure perceive NCDC's radio broadcast campaigns on COVID-19 to be reliable enough to affect the level of compliance to preventive measures passed across by NCDC through the major radio stations in the State. Lastly, it was revealed residents of Akure said that based on their exposure to NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocols in Akure, their level of compliance has increased considerably to a large extent, (Mean=3.8100). The implication of this is that NCDC's radio campaign messages are believed among Akure residents who consider it a reliable source of information in times of crisis, such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

Test of hypothesis

Hypothesis one: There is no significant relationship between exposure to NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 and COVID-19 protocol compliance among Akure residents of Ondo State

Table 3: Influence of exposure to NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 on COVID-19 protocol compliance among Akure residents of Ondo State

Variables	Mean	SD	r	N	p value	Remark
Exposure to NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19	3.8642	1.16297	0.01	346	0.000	Sig

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

*Sig. at 0.05 level

Table 4.3 shows that the mean of exposure to NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 was 3.8642, SD = 1.16297, while that of COVID-19 protocol compliance among Akure residents of Ondo State was 3.3208, SD = 1.32467. The correlation coefficient obtained was 0.01 with p-value > 0.05. This implies that there is a significant relationship between exposure to NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 and COVID-19 protocol compliance among Akure residents of Ondo State ($r = 0.01$, $N = 346$, $p > 0.05$). Based on the results, the null hypothesis one is rejected. This means that exposure to NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 among Akure residents significantly influenced COVID-19 protocol compliance rate among Akure residents in Ondo State.

Discussion of the findings

Research question one: What is the level of exposure to NCDC's radio campaigns on compliance with COVID-19 protocol among residents of Akure in Ondo State?

Findings revealed that there is a great level of exposure to Adaba FM, Orange FM, Breeze FM and OSRC's radio campaigns among Akure residents, and a high level of listenership to radio campaigns about COVID-19 in Akure on the major radio stations. Likewise, residents of Akure have come across NCDC's radio campaigns about COVID-19 compliance protocol on Adaba FM, Orange FM, Breeze FM and OSRC to a great extent. This finding aligns with the study of Akpobo (2015) that the mass media remain a crucial component and veritable tool in the campaign toward sustainable health development in Nigeria. This is so because through adequate health communication and campaigns on issues of health, the mass media have proven to be very concerned about our healthy development. The study also corroborates with the findings of Sixsmith et al. (2014) that media interventions utilise a variety of channels to inform, persuade, or motivate populations to guide them in the right direction in case of any disaster or outbreak of disease which can pose a significant threat to the public health. In like manner, the findings align with that of Akarika et al. (2020) that there is a high level of awareness campaigns on Coronavirus. The social responsibility theory can best explain this finding that, it is the responsibility of the media to provide timely and correct information for health education and the promotion of prevention strategies. Therefore, based on the principle of social responsibility theory, it is expected that the media become the primary source of information to the public in event of disasters and emergencies.

Research question two: What is the extent of compliance to NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol among residents of Akure in Ondo State?

Findings revealed that despite the considerably high level of awareness through NCDC's radio broadcast campaigns on COVID-19 in Akure, compliance among Akure residents of Ondo State is moderate on a general level. However, there is more compliance on an individual scale in Akure. It was likewise revealed that NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 protocol compliance passed across accurate, adequate and verified information to residents of Akure. Therefore, there is a high level of compliance with NCDC's COVID-19 protocols among people in Akure to a large extent. This level of compliance has increased considerably to a moderate extent due to exposure to NCDC's radio campaigns among Akure residents. This finding supports the findings of previous studies by Apuke and Omar (2021) that the media gave proper and adequate attention to the issues of the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria. It likewise corroborates with the findings of Cajetan et al. (2021) that most people are exposed to broadcast media campaigns on COVID-19 to a large extent, and this exposure is greatly reflected in their health status.

Hypothesis one: There is no significant relationship between exposure to NCDC's radio campaigns on COVID-19 and COVID-19 protocol compliance among residents of Akure in Ondo State

The finding revealed that exposure to radio campaigns on COVID-19 among Akure residents significantly influenced the COVID-19 protocol compliance rate among Akure residents in Ondo State. Based on the results, the null hypothesis one is rejected, implying that with constant exposure to radio campaigns on compliance with COVID-19 protocol, residents of Akure are bound to adhere to the contents of the campaign messages. This finding aligns with that of Emorinken (2020) and Oji (2020) that it was observed that radio served as a vital tool in creating awareness about the pandemic across Nigeria daily, it became a ritual for radio stations across the country to disseminate large scale information on the development that comes with the virus. This, therefore, served as awareness for members of the public, both in Nigeria and globally, disseminating information about the virus and enlightening people on the steps to take to avoid contracting the virus.

Summary, conclusion and recommendations

The study looked into the impact of NCDC's radio campaign on compliance with COVID-19 protocol among residents of Akure in Ondo State. Having researched the relevance of NCDC's radio broadcast campaigns in the area of information dissemination on important occurrences in the society, particularly on health communication regarding the COVID-19 outbreak and the quest to curb its spread through media messages, encouraging compliance with preventive measures, it was proven that radio serves as a viable medium of health communication and effecting compliance with COVID-19 protocol in Akure, the Ondo State capital. It was also observed that NCDC's radio campaigns are adequate to this effect which prompted exposure to the campaign messages and rightly educated residents of Akure on the virus and likewise affected a great level of compliance. Hence, to build on the gains against COVID-19 virus in Akure, more attention needs to be paid to radio campaigns on compliance with COVID-19 protocol as residents would get proper, adequate and timely updates on how best to curb the spread of the virus and make the society in general, a safe place to live in.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made.

- i. Although there is a high level of exposure to NCDC's radio campaigns on compliance with COVID-19 protocol among Residents of Akure in Ondo State, more attention should be paid to the contents of such campaign messages in order to effectively curb the spread of COVID-19.
- ii. Radio stations in Akure and NCDC should device means to restructure the contents of radio campaigns on compliance with COVID-19 protocol in a manner that is more appealing in order to effect a change in the compliance level among Akure residents.
- iii. Although Akure residents perceive information on NCDC's radio campaigns on compliance with COVID-19 protocol to be true and adequate, NCDC's radio campaigns should be intensified to dispel rumours about the pandemic as this will encourage most residents of Akure to take the issue serious and adhere to preventive protocol.
- iv. Radio stations in Akure and NCDC should continue campaigns on compliance with COVID-19 protocol in Akure even though, the virus infection rate has reduced as this will constantly bring to the consciousness of the need to practice compliance to preventive measures and further enhance the gains recorded against COVID-19.

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